

Impedance Sweep Frequency Response Analysis for the In-Situ Inspection of Distributed Stator Windings in Induction Motors

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Abstract—Impedance sweep frequency response analysis (SFRA) offers significant advantages as a non-destructive testing technique both for the ex-situ and in-situ inspection of rotating electrical machines and machine components. The diagnosis of squirrel cage induction motors (SCIMs) with random-wound stator windings via SFRA poses significant challenges due to the highly variable conductor positioning within the stator slots. This, combined with their widespread use in various industrial and transportation applications, has induced significant research attention on the application of SFRA to SCIMs. This work presents an extensive application of winding inspection using impedance spectroscopy measurements, in which a population of 22 SCIM specimens are tested via SFRA, where the variability of the machines' distributed winding is observable. Additionally, two different representation methods (i.e., bode and Nyquist impedance plots) are utilised to elucidate defective SCIMs using impedance spectroscopy as a means of in-situ inspection.

Index Terms—impedance spectroscopy, in-situ inspection, stator winding, induction motors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Squirrel Cage Induction Motors (SCIMs) are widely present in industrial applications, representing the largest electrical motor market share [1]. Despite their well-known robustness and reliability, they are not immune to failure or malfunction of their different constructive elements. Several studies report that millions of electrical motors are in operation, with thousands requiring repairs and being sent to service shops annually,

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only in the United States [2]. The improvement of inspection, diagnosis, and potential repair techniques of such dominant motor technology is thus a relevant and actual research topic.

Inspection and diagnosis of SCIMs in various power ratings are performed throughout their operational life, including quality control [3], periodic maintenance, or in-service monitoring [4]. However, most off-line electrical testing methods are common for ensuring and maintaining assets [5], [6]. Traditional off-line tests include AC and DC Hi-pot tests, insulation resistance measurement, polarization index, and surge testing, among others. These methods often target specific components of the stator insulation system for the detection of very particular failure mechanisms, or employ destructive protocols for "pass-off" test outcomes effectively reducing insulation life. However, no single test renders comprehensive, fast and reliable detection of all possible defects. In this context, sweep frequency response analysis (SFRA) emerges as a promising technique to detect a wide range of defects through a single non-destructive test [7].

In power transformers, SFRA is an established diagnostic method for identifying mechanical displacements and structural damages [8]. This methodology is also explored in the context of rotating electrical machines for different purposes. In [9], [10], the authors employ SFRA to diagnose short circuits in the field windings at the large salient poles of the hydrogenerators. Other works explored SFRA to track changes in single coil impedance profiles for different combinations of temperature and humidity conditions, as well as the effect of wire corrosion over exposure time [11]. Moreover, the effect of thermal cycling and combined thermal and mechanical stresses on the impedance profile of small coils is studied in [12]. The

effect of thermal cycling on the coils of a 2 MW aircraft generator was recently studied in [13] to map the degradation profile of the coil insulation system, while [14] provided the thermal failure profiles for the insulation system of these coils.

As such, SFRA has demonstrated the potential to be applied for the detection of different defects in fully assembled rotating machines. In the context of induction motors, numerous studies have extensively analysed impedance profiles under various short-circuit conditions, including phase-to-phase, inter-turn, and turn-to-ground faults [15], [16]. Some authors extended the application of SFRA to detect inductive-nature failures such as broken rotor bars in SCIM and damper winding in synchronous motors [17], [18]. Furthermore, the application of SFRA to assembled hairpin stators is used to detect defects in resin impregnation in [19]. Thus, the application of this technique offers significant advantages even in fully assembled machine specimens during both initial quality assurance and periodic maintenance tasks in service. The primary challenge to achieve repeatable and effective diagnosis of SFRA in SCIM lies in the nature of the stator windings, which are often randomly wound, leading to significant variability in the position of the conductor within the stator slots [20], [21]. This fact may mask potential signatures of defects at early stage.

This work presents the application of impedance SFRA for the offline in-situ inspection of a large population of identical SCIM specimens. This is performed on 22 induction motors with distributed stator windings, while being disconnected from the electric drive (offline), to statistically account for a representative population of machines and to enhance the method's reliability through repeatability evaluation for in-situ inspection, despite the randomly-wound nature of the stator winding in these machines. Moreover, two different impedance representation methodologies are utilised to better discern between healthy and potentially defective specimens, notably the sweep frequency response-based analysis (SFRA) by means of impedance spectroscopy as well as the representation via the impedance Nyquist locus. The utilised measurements along with the discussed representations render reliable diagnostic results as an in-situ machine inspection method for the direct discrimination of machines with faulty windings. Additionally, the discussed technique enables the localisation of the identified defects within specific machine phases by the comparative analysis of the extracted representations. The manuscript is organised as follows: Section II offers theoretical insights of ex-situ and in-situ inspection of SCIMs and the technique's potential to detect a variety of defects. Section III presents the experimental measurement framework and the utilised equipment along with the selected population of 22 SCIMs under test. Section IV analyses the broadband impedance spectroscopy results by the impedance bode plots and Nyquist locus. Finally, Section V poses the study's conclusions and future work directions.

II. IMPEDANCE SFRA FOR STATOR WINDINGS

This section aims to provide the physical background behind SFRA for the in-situ inspection of electromechanical device

windings, notably electrical machine drives. The impedance SFRA response of machine windings depends on several parameters and factors. According to multi-conductor transmission line theory, each machine conductor within a slot exhibits unique per-unit-length parameters, including shunt capacitance (C), conductance (G), series resistance (R), and inductance (L) [22]. These depend on factors such as the surrounding space and neighbouring conductor bodies, as well as factors such as intrinsic winding insulation material structure, thickness and geometry. Fig. 1 shows the lumped-pi equivalent circuit of a motor winding following multi-conductor transmission line theory, where each conductor is represented separately.

Fig. 1. Equivalent per-turn lumped-pi circuit model of a coil incorporating slot and end-winding sections [23], [24].

Electrical machine windings adopt several shapes depending on a wide variety of factors such as power rating, rated voltage, or manufacturing requirements, among others. The randomly wound winding is the most prevalent type and is widely employed in low-power, low-voltage applications. In this configuration, the relative positioning of the turns with respect to the machine core varies in a non-deterministic manner. Consequently, the per-unit-length parameters of the transmission line system vary even for twin windings and machines, in contrast to hairpin or form windings, which exhibit a more consistent coil conductor shaping and relative positioning. Fig. 2 shows an illustrated comparison between fixed-conductor positioning in a form or hairpin winding context versus the case of random-wound round conductors in a distributed winding.

The inspection of windings in electrical machines can be performed in-situ or ex-situ (i.e., previously disassembled or embedded within the machine stator body, notably the ferromagnetic material core). The in-situ SFRA poses increased complexity due to the presence of a laminated stator iron core. This iron core is normally grounded, and thus parasitic capacitances and conductances depend on the insulation geometry, materials, and conductor positioning. The presence of the iron core mainly affects series resistance and inductance due to

Fig. 2. Slot cross-section of a randomly-wound (left) and a form-wound (right) winding, including single conductor per-unit-length parameters.

increased core flux linkage at low frequencies and shielding effect at high frequencies [23].

III. TEST HARDWARE

For the purposes of this work, a sample of 22 identical induction motors as received by the manufacturer were used for the inspection of their windings using SFRA as shown in Fig. 3. These $1.1kW$ motors embed a Δ -connected random-wound single-layer distributed winding over 36 stator slots with a die-cast aluminium rotor cage containing 46 rotor bars. For every machine, SFRA is applied to each phase (line-to-line) to examine the frequency responses of the impedance in amplitude and phase angle as well as the orbit plots of the Nyquist locus.

The application of electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) as a SFRA technique was facilitated with the WK-6500B impedance analyser shown in Fig. 3 for inspection purposes, used in the same application as presented in [13]- [14], [25]. This analyser is designed to sweep through a frequency range of 100 Hz to 50 MHz , allowing for a complete mapping of the broadband frequency impedance of the winding connection. The device requires careful calibration allowing the analyser to compensate for any high frequency noise, picked up by the device fixture. A short circuit, open circuit and high frequency calibration check are performed, using strictly the routine calibration standards provided by the manufacturer.

Fig. 3. Specimen of induction machines under test from the batch of the 22 induction motors examined in this study.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b illustrate the amplitude and phase of the impedance frequency response for phase W-U for all of the 22 induction motor specimens measured under SFRA in this study, while Fig. 5 depicts a close-up view in the inductive peak of the impedance, notably the first resonance of the coil connection under test. Additionally, Fig. 6 presents the impedance orbit plot of the impedance locus with respect to frequency. Through Fig. 4 and Fig. 6, it is seen that there is a consistency in the impedance response for phase W-U for 21 of the 22 induction motors inspected with SFRA. However, one of the examined SCIMs (Motor #9) exhibits an abnormal behaviour in terms of resonance peak both in the amplitude and phase angle responses as observed through Fig. 4 and the Nyquist locus of Fig. 4b.

For the specimen of Motor #9, the inductive peak of the amplitude response appears at the resonant frequency of 0.88 MHz with a peak impedance value of $222\ \Omega$ for phase W-U, compared to the other 21 motors of the examined batch having an average value of 1.61 MHz for the resonant frequency with an average peak impedance value of $360\ \Omega$. This provides an initial defect indication for one of the two phases, either phase W or U, being under test in this inspection measurement. Figures 5 and 6 reveal another slight outlier in Motor #11, which exhibits a slightly higher peak in Fig. 5 and the largest locus in Fig. 6. Furthermore, Table I presents the averaged relative difference for each tested motor and connection. These values are computed by summing the impedance amplitude across all frequency points and subsequently normalising by the total number of considered points. Table I provides a quantitative comparison among all

analysed motor specimens and inspected connections.

Similar to Fig. 4, Fig. 7 presents the impedance plots for the W-V phase inspection. The amplitude response, phase angle, and impedance orbits are shown in Figs. 7a, 7b, and 8, respectively, with the latter using Nyquist plots. At this inspection stage, it is evident through all the subplots of Fig. 7 that there is very precise consistency in the behaviour of phase W-V for all 22 motors cases in terms of the frequency responses and Nyquist orbits. From these observations, it is obvious that phase W-V exhibits no outlier values and is as such deemed as healthy with satisfying accuracy. This is also confirmed in Table I, where the average relative amplitude difference for motor #9 remains at 9.55 % compared to the 20.95% observed for the W-U connection. For all the specimen in the population of 22 induction motors, the inductive peak of the amplitude response appears at the frequency around

Fig. 4. Impedance SFRA by inspection of the phase W-U with impedance spectroscopy for the 22 induction motors examined: a) amplitude response, and b) phase angle response.

Fig. 5. Close-up view of the inductive peak at the first resonance of the phase W-U with impedance spectroscopy for the 22 induction motors examined.

Fig. 6. Impedance Nyquist locus plot for Phase W-U by SFRA inspection in all 22 motors examined.

1.57 MHz with a peak impedance value of 371 Ω. Motor #11 shows similar trend compared to connection W-U with slightly increased amplitude in the resonant peak and larger Nyquist locus orbit in the imaginary axes.

Further, Fig. 9 shows the Nyquist locus for connection U-V where the Motor #9 outlier behaviour and the slight deviation of Motor #11 are clearly observed. The application SFRA for the inspection of phase U-V renders the responses presented through Fig. 10. Through the latter figure, it is observed that both the amplitude and angle as well as the Nyquist plot for phase U-V reveal an outlier value for Motor #9 as observed for the inspection of phase W-U in Fig. 4. For the discussed outlier specimen of Motor #9, the inductive peak of the amplitude response appears at the resonant frequency of 0.90 MHz with a peak impedance value of 224 Ω, compared to the other

TABLE I
AVERAGE RELATIVE DIFFERENCE FOR EACH TESTED MOTOR AND
LINE-TO-LINE MEASUREMENT

Motor sample	U-V [%]	W-U [%]	V-W [%]
Motor #1	10.21	11.79	8.01
Motor #2	6.32	5.24	6.92
Motor #3	7.19	3.21	4.61
Motor #4	8.62	13.44	12.13
Motor #5	8.64	6.99	7.49
Motor #6	8.35	13.50	11.04
Motor #7	9.11	8.91	6.74
Motor #8	12.95	13.88	13.46
Motor #9	22.28	20.95	9.55
Motor #10	7.66	9.47	5.87
Motor #11	17.97	18.11	16.69
Motor #12	9.55	4.32	6.80
Motor #13	12.33	13.80	12.83
Motor #14	7.18	6.64	6.83
Motor #15	7.05	7.55	4.74
Motor #16	9.17	6.43	8.80
Motor #17	8.76	6.21	4.39
Motor #18	8.09	10.75	8.84
Motor #19	9.9	7.31	6.91
Motor #20	5.96	7.03	4.66
Motor #21	9.35	7.47	11.82
Motor #22	9.95	10.11	9.80

21 motors of the examined batch having an average value of 1.65 MHz for the resonant frequency with an average peak impedance value of 385 Ω.

The presence of Motor #9 outlier in phase connections W-U and U-V leads to the conclusion that a defect is present in the winding part corresponding to stator coils grouped in phase U, as this is the phase involved in the measurements illustrated through Fig. 4, Fig. 6, Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. Table I quantifies the Motor #9 deviation for the connections involving phase U, where averaged relative deviations of 22.28 %, 20.95% and 9.55% are found for connections U-V, W-U, and V-W respectively. The U-V phase plots shown in Fig. 10, identify Motor #11 as an outlier as observed for previously inspected connections. Thus, the abnormal behaviour for Motor #11 is present in all three phase-phase plots. Looking at all three Nyquist loci for this particular machine through Figures 6, 8 and 9, the expanded locus shows a minor defect or potential minor degradation pattern similar to the results shown in [13] and [14] over the "coil useful life" span as referred to in the latter work. This indicates that this machine specimen has been exposed to a more progressed level of degradation, either electrical or electrothermal, compared to the other machines in the examined population or exhibits an inherent electrical defect. However, this is still within tolerance values in terms of thresholds for a failure alarm, as the only observed effect is the increase in its peak impedance value without any shift in the resonant frequency value [11], [12], [13], [14], [15]. On the contrary, Motor #9 raises more significant alarms as by the latter works it exhibits a tangible reduction in the real

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Impedance SFRA by inspection of the phase W-V with impedance spectroscopy for the 22 induction motors examined in this study: a) amplitude response (close-up view of the inductive peak at the first resonance), and b) overall phase response.

and imaginary part of the impedance which manifests as a shrinking of the Nyquist locus. However, further investigation is required for the exact characterisation of the defect or fault type as well as for the evaluation of potential degradation in the conductors of the stator winding coils for the phases determined as outlier cases in the batch.

From the presented SFRA analysis for each phase in the stator winding in the population of 22 motors, it is seen that impedance spectroscopy renders a valuable tool in terms of defect identification in the distributed stator winding by the measured line impedance in-situ as well as for the identification of outlier values in the windings of new, as-manufactured machines. From the batch of 22 as manufactured induction motors inspected in this study, only Motor #9 and Motor #11 manifest outlier values in terms of frequency response

Fig. 8. Impedance Nyquist locus plot for Phase W-V by SFRA inspection in all 22 motors examined.

Fig. 9. Impedance Nyquist locus plot for Phase U-V by SFRA inspection in all 22 motors examined.

patterns in amplitude and phase angle, peak impedance at resonance and impedance orbit plot by the Nyquist diagrams representation. Recent studies on stator coil insulation assessment and impedance spectroscopy [7], [12]–[14], [25] suggest that a potential electrical defect is present in one of the phases of Motor #9, while Motor #11 exhibits a minor inherent imbalance in one of its phases. Despite the ability of SFRA to localise the measured asymmetries within a phase of the machine, further investigation is required to characterise precisely the type of defect and its severity level. However, a reliable diagnostic decision can be made regarding fault location within a specific phase of the machine winding. At the same time, the utilised representations show the potential for enhanced health evaluation by the identification of the defect’s extent through the distances observed during the shifting of the impedance peaks in the amplitude and phase angle response over frequency as well as by the expansion or shrinking of the impedance Nyquist locus.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 10. Impedance SFRA by inspection of the phase U-V with impedance spectroscopy for the 22 induction motors examined in this study: a) amplitude response (close-up view of the inductive peak at the first resonance), and b) overall phase response.

V. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

In this work, impedance spectroscopy was applied as a means of in situ inspection of distributed stator windings in a batch of 22 induction motors manufactured and received by the supplier chain. The implementation of impedance sweep frequency response analysis (SFRA) and its potential to provide a diagnostic tool for defects in the stator winding of each motor in the selected population of machines was investigated. In terms of health evaluation, the examined population demonstrated consistency in their frequency responses for all 22 machines in the examined batch, except for two specific motors from the batch (Motor #9 and Motor #11) that were identified as outlier values. Further characterisation of these enabled the localisation of the tracked defects in

specific phases and facilitated a discussion on the potential characterisation of the defect nature in each case. The findings are consistent with the recent body of literature elaborating on such defects and fault types, showing the potential of non-destructive testing by impedance SFRA tools for the in-situ inspection of distributed stator windings in electrical machine.

With regards to future work, it can be noted that although the utilisation of impedance SFRA carries added value and provides compelling results for the identification of such outliers and for the relative localisation of the defect within the phase it pertains to, there are still elements of this technique to investigate in terms of discriminating the fault type without requiring stator disassembly and intrinsic visual inspection. These pertain to the future scope of the presented work both for the in-situ inspection of the stand-alone machine as well as for the impedance frequency response for the integrated system of the machine connected to the power electronics as an integrated electric drive.

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